

A good data model is worth a complex neural network: Evidence from building generalization using deep learning

Zhiyong Zhou^{*,**}, Jan Winkler^{***}, Cheng Fu^{****}, and Robert Weibel^{*}

^{*}Department of Geography, University of Zurich, Zurich, CH

^{**}Department of Geography, University of Wisconsin-Madison, Madison, USA

^{***}Datahouse AG, Zurich, CH

^{****}College of Information and Electrical Engineering, China Agricultural University, Beijing, CN

Abstract

Deep learning (DL) has provided a new paradigm to improve the automation of map generalization to produce legible multi-scale maps. To date, learning map generalization has mainly been treated as analogous to the image prediction task in computer vision by taking raster maps as input. However, due to limitations of available datasets and the rapid evolution of neural network architectures, the applicability of some empirical findings (e.g., data models representing map objects) about training DL models for map generalization remains uncertain. This study focuses on the generalization of the most common topographic features, buildings, and investigates the roles of data models and different complexities of neural network architectures in learning building generalization in raster maps. Specifically, single-channel and two-channel data models were created, respectively. In addition to the previously commonly used convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture, U-Net, a more advanced architecture distinct from CNN, Swin Transformer, was introduced to learn building generalization. A series of experiments controlled by the data model and the neural network were conducted based on two datasets, OSM-Stuttgart and swisstopo-Zurich. The results show that building generalization models trained with the two-channel data models consistently outperform those trained with the single-channel data model. Moreover, U-Net outperforms Swin Transformer for building generalization in both datasets. These results highlight the importance of data models for the downstream learning task, e.g., building generalization in this study.

Keywords: Raster map, Building generalization, Data model, U-Net, Swin Transformer

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1. Introduction

Map generalization is a fundamental process to visualize geographical features and highlight different geographical phenomena at multiple scales (Mackaness, Burghardt, and Duchêne 2014). It involves a series of operations on individual and groups of map objects, such as elimination, enlargement, simplification, aggregation, typification, etc. (Regnauld and McMaster 2007). Therefore, its automation has been pursued extensively, which can significantly ease the manual effort of expert cartographers to generalize maps that contain a large number of geographical features (Tobler 1964; Brassel and Weibel 1988; Powitz 1993; Weibel 1997; Sester 2005; Regnauld et al. 2014). Conventional automated map generalization methods are mainly focused on the algorithmic paradigm, such as algorithms for individual generalization operators (Stanislawski et al. 2014) and the overall process chaining multiple operators (Harrie and Weibel 2007). However, the algorithmic paradigm still strongly relies on the formalization of cartographic generalization knowledge and the parameter setting of algorithms by expert cartographers, thus impeding their capacity and flexibility to cope with varying generalization scenarios composed of different geographical features.

The emergence of deep learning has provided a new opportunity to improve the automation of map generalization (Touya, Zhang, and Lokhat 2019; Harrie et al. 2024; Kang, Gao, and Roth 2024). Currently, learning map generalization across scales is implemented more frequently in raster maps than in vector maps. Raster map generalization can be adapted from deep learning (DL) models for computer vision (CV) and provides end-to-end solutions, although some individual generalization operators can be learned better on vector maps (Zhou, Fu, and Weibel 2023; Yan and Yang 2024; Cui et al. 2025). For example, (Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019) empirically investigated the capacities of several representative neural networks from CV (i.e., U-Net, Residual U-Net, and GAN) to generalize buildings in raster maps. Some subsequent studies further improved the ability of these original CV DL models in map generalization by adjusting the input data models (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024), customizing loss functions (Courtial, Touya, and Zhang 2023; Kang et al. 2020), and adapting neural network architectures (Zhou, Fu, and Weibel 2024).

However, previous studies were mostly evaluated with only a single dataset. Thus, it is unclear whether the empirical findings (e.g., feasibility of the proposed data model (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024), comparative capacities of different NN types (Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019)) about training a DL model for map generalization also apply to other datasets or not. Furthermore, while the rapid advance of deep learning has given birth to many newer and more complex neural network architectures, existing studies on DL-based map generalization have not timely echoed such an advance and examined the capacities of such newer networks.

To address the limitations mentioned above, this study takes the research results of (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024) as a starting point and further explores the roles of (a) the spatial data model and (b) the neural network architecture in learning building generalization in raster maps. Specifically, we chose a Transformer architecture, Swin Transformer, as a new and more complex neural network to perform building generalization, which we then compared with the results of the baseline model, U-Net, as reported in (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024). The rationale for choosing the Transformer architecture lies in its distinct mathematical procedure (i.e., the attention mechanism

(Vaswani et al. 2017)) to process the input data and the proved capability of the Transformer in semantic segmentation of images (Dosovitskiy et al. 2020; Liu et al. 2021). Furthermore, we examine the feasibility of the two-channel data model proposed by (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024) in two neural networks with two data sources (i.e., OSM-Stuttgart (Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019) and swisstopo-Zurich (Senn et al. 2024)) and compare its performance to the single-channel data model. The contributions of this study are two-fold:

- With the Swin Transformer, the two-channel data model still achieved higher performance than the single-channel data model in both the OSM-Stuttgart and swisstopo-Zurich datasets, confirming the better capacity of the two-channel data model proposed in (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024).
- More interestingly, the complex neural network, Swin Transformer, was found not to achieve higher performance than the simpler neural network, U-Net, by using the same two-channel data model, implying that choosing a good data model can be more important than using a complex neural network in learning building generalization.

2. Methodology

2.1. Problem statement

Map generalization, including building generalization, in raster data models is typically formulated as an image prediction problem. As illustrated in Figure 1, given a binary image building map at the source scale (e.g., 1:10,000), where 1 (i.e., white) denotes the pixels occupied by a building and 0 (i.e., black) denotes the non-building pixels. The objective of learning building generalization through a neural network is to predict a raster map, in which the arrangement of buildings complies with the cartographic constraints at the target scale (e.g., 1:25,000).

Figure 1: Source scale (1:10,000) and target scale (1:25,000) map of the same size (e.g., 224x224 pixel in this study).

2.2. Neural networks

To investigate whether more advanced and complex neural network architectures may better fit the task of learning building generalization in raster maps, we introduce the Swin Transformer in addition to the U-net architecture previously demonstrated as feasible (Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019; Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024).

2.2.1. U-Net

U-Net is a classical CNN architecture for image segmentation. Previous studies have shown the good capability of the U-Net for building generalization (Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019; Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024). Refer to (Ronneberger, Fischer, and Brox 2015) for the details of the original architecture.

2.2.2. Shifting Window (Swin) Transformer

Transformers, first introduced for natural language processing (Vaswani et al. 2017), have since been successfully adapted to computer vision (Dosovitskiy et al. 2020; Liu et al. 2021). For our building generalization task, we selected the Swin Transformer as a representative architecture. It takes an input image, splits it into non-overlapping patches (Figure 2) that act as tokens, and calculates self-attention for each. In subsequent steps, the patches are merged to reduce the number of tokens and increasing the field of view. This token-merging operation is applied in four hierarchical stages (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Illustration of how the Swin Transformer approaches patch partition and how the shifted window approach operates (from Liu et al. (2021)).

Figure 3: Overview of the Swin Transformer (tiny version) architecture (from Liu et al. (2021)).

2.3. Data models

A data model denotes how individual objects and relationships among objects can be organized and represented. For a neural network, the data model determines the representation of the input data, and in a computer vision task, this typically refers to images with a defined number of channels (e.g., RGB) that are fed to a model. In this study, we investigate two representation approaches for buildings in the source-scale and target-scale maps.

2.3.1. Single-channel data model

The single-channel data model is the original data model used in (Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019). As shown in Figure 4, a patch of the input source scale map and its corresponding patch of the target scale map (also called ground truth) are represented as a raster data model with one binary channel of a predefined size (224x224 pixels in our case), respectively. With this approach, the model has to predict all the buildings visible in the given scene.

Figure 4: Single-channel data model for the input and target patch.

2.3.2. Two-channel data model

In the two-channel approach, the input data is divided into two channels (Figure 5), the focal channel and the contextual channel. Specifically, the focal channel contains the focal building, while the contextual channel represents the buildings surrounding the focal building. In this approach, the neural network predicts only the focal building. There are two types of two-channel data model: one with placement of the focal building in the center of a patch (centered-focal building) and one with random placement of the focal building (random-focal building).

Figure 5: Schematic overview of the two-channel data model, stacking two individual channels into one single image.

Centered-focal building. As illustrated in Figure 6, the focal building is always placed in the center of a patch. For details of the two-channel centered-focal building data model, refer to (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024).

Figure 6: Example of a patch with two channels and centered-focal building placement. The focal building is shown in black, and context buildings are shown in gray.

Random-focal building. Although (Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024) has demonstrated the advantages of the centered-focal building two-channel data model for learning map generalization, their approach can be considered as a data augmentation strategy, yielding a larger size of the training dataset compared to the single-channel data model by iteratively placing each building in the center of a patch. Hence, we propose the two-channel random-focal building data model by randomly selecting a building from a given input-target patch pair (as shown in Figure 7), which guarantees the same size of the training data as the single-channel data model.

Figure 7: Example of a patch with two channels and random-focal building placement.

3. Experiments

We conducted a series of experiments, controlling both the input data models and the neural networks employed. The main questions addressed by the experiments are:

1. Given the same neural network (i.e., Swin Transformer), how will the input data models influence the learning of building generalization in raster maps?
2. Given the same data model, will a more advanced neural network architecture, the Swin Transformer, outperform the classical CNN architecture, the U-Net, on building generaliza-

tion?

3.1. Experimental setup

3.1.1 Datasets

To more comprehensively investigate the roles of data models and neural networks in learning building generalization in raster maps, two sources were used: *OSM-Stuttgart*⁰ and *swisstopo-Zurich*¹. The generalization in both data sources is from 1:10,000 to 1:25,000. The detailed description can be found in Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019 and Senn et al. 2024; Zhou, Fu, and Weibel 2024. Following the definition of data models as elaborated in Section 2.3 and the predefined patch size setting of 224x224 pixels, six datasets were created to train and test building generalization models. The basic information for the six datasets is shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the test set was first created by choosing 5% of the original data. Then, the training and validation data were randomly selected using a 90% / 10% training / validation split from the remaining data of each dataset.

Table 1: Datasets created, organized by data sources and data models. For brevity, in the following the single-channel model will be abbreviated as *1-Ch*, the two-channel centered-focal building model as *2-Ch-Cen*, and the two-channel random-focal building model as *2-Ch-Rnd*.

Data source	Data model	Number of patches
OSM-Stuttgart	single-channel	29854
	two-channel	89048
	centered-focal-building	
	two-channel	29854
	random-focal-building	
swisstopo-Zurich	single-channel	36672
	two-channel	72096
	centered-focal-building	
	two-channel	36672
	random-focal-building	

3.1.2 Implementation details

The neural networks used for building generalization were implemented with Python 3.9 and PyTorch 1.11.0. They were trained based on the created six datasets, respectively, using the S3IT Science Cluster’s CPUs and GPUs (NVIDIA Tesla V100) of the University of Zurich (UZH). For the first experimental question, involving only the Swin Transformer, we used a batch size of 32 to reduce computational cost given the model’s high training demands. For the second question, which compared Swin Transformer and U-Net architectures, we used a smaller batch size of 8 to introduce more variation in training updates, which can help models adapt better to new data. The models were trained with binary cross-entropy (BCE) loss, and optimized using AdamW.

0. <https://github.com/yuzzfeng/MapGen>

1. Open data version based on the swisstopo *Swiss Map Vector* products (<https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/en/national-maps-swiss-map-vector>) in preparation.

3.1.3 Evaluation metrics

For comparability with prior studies Feng, Thiemann, and Sester 2019; Fu, Zhou, Xin, et al. 2024, we also used the Intersection over Union (IoU) to assess the similarity of geometric shapes between the predicted generalized map and the target map. However, as the generalization level between the source scale and target scale is highly skewed, that is, more than a half of buildings in the data experience very minor or even no generalization, we report the median IoU (mIoU) to evaluate the generalization performance of trained models.

3.2. Comparison of results

3.2.1 By data model

To address the first experimental question, six models were trained for building generalization based on the Swin Transformer and the six datasets listed in Table 1. The test results are reported in Table 2. With the OSM-Stuttgart data source, while both two-channel data models, 2-Ch-Cen and 2-Ch-Rnd, achieved higher mIoU than the single-channel data model (mIoU: 0.961), the 2-Ch-Cen data model’s mIoU (0.974) was higher than that (0.965) of the 2-Ch-Rnd data model. With the swisstopo-Zurich data source, the 2-Ch-Rnd data model performed best with the highest mIoU of 0.951, followed by the 2-Ch-Cen data model (mIoU: 0.941) and the 1-Ch data model with the lowest mIoU of 0.915.

Table 2: Building generalization performance of Swin Transformer on different datasets.

Data source	Data model	mIoU
OSM-Stuttgart	1-Ch	0.961
	2-Ch-Cen	0.974
	2-Ch-Rnd	0.965
swisstopo-Zurich	1-Ch	0.915
	2-Ch-Cen	0.941
	2-Ch-Rnd	0.951

3.2.2. By neural network architecture

To address the second experimental question, the Swin Transformer and U-Net were trained based on the two data sources and a fixed data model, 2-Ch-Cen, respectively. The rationale to choose the 2-Ch-Cen data model lies mainly in the larger training dataset size derived from this data model. As reported in Table 3, in the OSM-Stuttgart data source, the mIoU of U-Net was 0.999, higher than that of Swin Transformer, 0.978. Likewise, in the swisstopo-Zurich data source, U-Net also outperformed Swin Transformer, with an mIoU of 0.958 vs. 0.942.

4. Discussion

In response to the first experimental question about the role of spatial data models, it is evident that the two-channel data models, regardless of whether it is the centered-focal building approach or the random-focal-building approach, are superior to the single-channel data model in enabling the Swin Transformer to learn building generalization. Notably, it was originally hypothesized that the better capacity of the two-channel centered-focal building data model as reported in Fu,

Table 3: Building generalization performance of different neural network architectures.

Data source	Neural network	mIoU
OSM-Stuttgart	U-Net	0.999
	Swin Transformer	0.978
swissTopo-Zurich	U-Net	0.958
	Swin Transformer	0.942

Zhou, Xin, et al. 2024 may be attributed to the increased size of the training dataset by taking each building of the data source as a patch. However, as shown in Table 2, the higher performance of the 2-Ch-Rnd data model, which results in the same patches as the single-channel approach, indicates the better capacity of the layering data representation (i.e., two-channel stacking of a focal building channel and contextual building channel) itself for learning building generalization in raster maps. It further underlines the importance of a good data model for a neural network in learning map generalization Fu, Zhou, Feng, et al. 2024 as well as other geospatial AI tasks Mai et al. 2025.

In terms of the second question posed in our experiments about the role of neural network architectures, the results with both data sources, OSM-Stuttgart and swisstopo-Zurich Section 4.2.2, clearly demonstrate that U-Net is a better neural network architecture than Swin-Transformer for building generalization in raster maps. Furthermore, the complexity of Swin Transformer trained model (parameter number: ~ 85 million) was almost triple that of U-Net trained model (parameter number: ~ 30 million). This implies that a more complex neural network is not necessarily more capable of a learning task, such as building generalization in raster maps in our case.

Synthesizing the results of Section 3.2, we therefore argue that a good data model, which is mainly created from domain knowledge, can be both simpler and, even more importantly, more effective for a learning task than a complex neural network.

5. Conclusion

With this study, we sought to deepen the understanding of the roles of data models and neural network architectures of different complexity in learning building generalization in raster maps. The experiments with two data sources show that the two-channel data models consistently enable Swin Transformer to learn building generalization better than the single-channel data model. Furthermore, the more complex neural network architecture, Swin Transformer, does not show higher performance than U-Net. Therefore, we want to highlight the importance of data models in deep learning and argue that a good data model can be worth a complex neural network for downstream tasks. In the future, more complex neural networks will be continuously introduced to cartographic tasks, such as building generalization in raster maps. That is, future work should not only explore the capacity of new deep learning techniques for map generalization but also further examine the applicability of the findings and arguments of this study.

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